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**STYLISTIC INVERSION AS A MEANS OF EXPRESSION
EMOTIONALITY AND EXPRESSIVENESS IN ENGLISH LITERATURE
OF THE XIX-XX CENTURIES**

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Annotation. It is known that inversion, also called anastrophe, in literary style and rhetoric, the syntactic reversal of the normal order of the words and phrases in a sentence, as, in English, the placing of an adjective after the noun it modifies the form, a verb before its subject, or a noun preceding its preposition. Inversion is most commonly used in poetry in which it may both satisfy the demands of the metre and achieve emphasis.

Key words: language, inversion, emotionality, expressiveness, literature, stylistic, grammatical, distinguish

Unlike Uzbek or Russian, which are characterized by a free order of words in a sentence, English is notable for a fixed order of words in a sentence and belongs to the class of analytical languages. So, if in synthetic languages it is possible to freely rearrange words in a sentence to make speech expressive, then in English it is often impossible to do this without breaking the syntactic connections between words and without changing the meaning of the entire sentence. Due to this, many

linguists have tried to determine the functions that word order performs in an English sentence. In particular, the famous Russian linguist Alexander Smirnitsky distinguished the following functions [4, p.62]:

- 1) Grammatical function (expression of the word order of certain syntactic expressions);
- 2) Expression of the lexical subject and lexical predicate by the order of words (determination of the direction of communication between words);
- 3) Expressive and stylistic function (highlighting certain words with intonation or stress).

Despite the fact that the word order plays an important role, the author may deviate from it for his own purposes, using the so-called inversion.

Before talking about the types of inversion, it is necessary to give this concept a clear definition. I.V. Arnold understands the following by inversion: "A violation of the usual order of the members of a sentence, as a result of which an element is highlighted and receives special connotations of emotionality or expressiveness, is called inversion"[1, p.112]. A similar definition is given by V.N. Komissarov: "Inversion is a deviation from the usual ("direct") order of arrangement of sentence members, used as an effective way of expressing emotional characteristics of the utterance"[3, p.148].

There are many classifications of inversion, but many authors agree that inversion can be grammatical and stylistic. Grammatical inversion is not stylistically marked, it expresses general grammatical rules, and is usually used to construct interrogative sentences.:

- **Were they** on the same side of the path as the moor-gate? (A.K. Doyle, "The Dog Baskervilles")

In this sentence, the predicate **were** stands before the subject **they**, i.e. there is not a direct word order, which carries grammatical information that this is an interrogative sentence. Also, some linguists refer to grammatical inversion sentences with the construction There is/are:

• **There is no doubt** that she perfectly idolized him. (C. Dickens, "Great Hopes")

Sentences with such a construction are also a case of the reverse order of words in a sentence, since in them the predicate actually stands before the subject, but when at the same time, the word order does not carry any stylistic coloring.

The study of the types of grammatical inversion does not arouse interest, since they are commonplace both in oral and written speech. The same cannot be said about stylistic inversion, which we will consider in more detail.

Having studied the most common types of stylistic inversion in the works of English authors of the XIX-XX century, the following main groups can be distinguished [1, p.222]:

1. The predicate of a compound nominal predicate precedes the subject. The predicative precedes the connective verb and the subject;
2. Putting circumstances in the first place;
3. Putting a direct supplement in the first place;

The first type is a predicative, which can be expressed by a noun, an adjective, or a predicate of a compound nominal predicate precedes a connective verb and a subject. This type of inversion is usually found for colloquial speech, but it is also typical for book speech. For example:

• **A good generous prayer** it was (M. Twain, "The Adventures of Tom Sawyer")[2, c.186].

• "How **fond** she is of finding morals in things!" (L. Carroll, "Alice in Wonderland")

In this type of inverted sentences, the logical stress is transferred to the verb, in order to emphasize the evaluative characteristics of the utterance. The second type is putting circumstances (circumstantial words) in the first place. In this type of inversion, emphasis is placed not only on the circumstance itself, but also on the subject, which is placed in the last place, which is an emphatic position. For example:

- **On the left of his great leaders at the poetic Snodgrass**, and near him again the sporting Winkle ... (C. Dickens, "Posthumous Notes of the Pickwick Club").

- **Here comes the mare**, said Joe, ringing like a peal of bells!(Ch.Dickens, "Great Expectations")

In addition, a special liveliness and dynamism of the narrative is created by putting the postpositive in the first place:

- In another moment **down went Alice** after it, never once considering how in the world she was to get out again. (L. Carroll, "Alice in Wonderland")

Inversion in cases of **down went Alice** shows the surprise of Alice's fall and therefore is stylistically relevant.

The third type is putting a direct supplement in the first place. This type of inversion is used to give a thought a special expressiveness by deliberately highlighting. Cases of complement inversion found in fiction, they are remembered as curiosities [2, p.185]:

- **Talent** Mr. Micawber has. **Capital** Mr. Micawber has not. (C. Dickens. "Life David Copperfield, told by himself")

Having considered the features of the artistic language of the works of English authors XIX-XX centuries. we came to the conclusion that one of the most striking stylistic means is inversion. It serves as a means of emotionality and expressiveness, expresses the author's desire to emphasize what should be seen by the reader, and also serves as a means of expressing the author's individuality.

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